

Plant regeneration and screening from long-term NaCl-stressed rice callus

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Salinity is one of the major causes of reduced productivity in rice growing areas. Tissue culture could complement breeding techniques to produce variants which are tolerant of salt. The objectives of our study were to regenerate rice plants from long-term NaCl-stressed callus of variety Reiho and to determine if there is a direct relationship between tolerance for salt at the cellular level and at the plant level.

Dehulled mature seeds of variety Reiho were surface-sterilized with 70% ethyl alcohol followed by 0.1% mercuric chloride, then washed 4 times with sterile distilled water. The seeds were inoculated on Murashige and Skoog's medium (MSYC) with 2 mg 2,4-D/liter, 2 g casein hydrolysate/liter, 2 g yeast extract/liter, 30 g sucrose/liter and 8 g agar/liter at pH 5.8. The induced calli were allowed to proliferate for 4 wk (1 passage).

The proliferated calli were inoculated on selection medium (MSYC with 15 g NaCl/liter) and transferred to fresh medium every 4 wk. The cultures were kept in darkness with temperature maintained at 26-27 °C. After 32 passages, calli were transferred to Linsmaier and Skoog's regeneration medium with 1 mg benzylaminopurine/liter, 0.5 mg α-naphthaleneacetic acid/liter, 40 g sucrose/liter, and 8 g agar/liter at pH 5.8. The cultures were kept under continuous light (3 klx) at 26-27 °C.

Eighteen individual calli stressed with NaCl were transferred to regeneration medium and only 30% produced plants totalling 35. The regenerated plants were grown in Yoshida's culture solution for 30 d and then transferred to the same

The response of calli of variety Reiho in different concentrations of NaCl.

Treatment (g NaCl/liter)	Initial weight ^a (g)	Final weight (g)	Relative increase in weight ^b (%)
0	0.0498	0.6882	1281.93
5	0.0513	0.6446	1156.53
10	0.0512	0.4551	788.87
15	0.0497	0.2762	455.73
20	0.0521	0.1607	208.44

^a Average of 10 calli.

^b $\frac{\text{Final weight} - \text{initial weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100$.

solution with different concentrations of NaCl: 0, 5, 10, and 15 g/liter.

Although the calli tolerated exposure to 1.5% NaCl for 32 passages (32 mo), the regenerated plants did not survive when grown in culture solution containing 5, 10, and 15 g NaCl/liter. Plants kept on control (no NaCl) flowered, but showed 100% sterility. The regenerated plants did not carry the NaCl tolerance trait present in the calli.

The regenerated plants exposed to different concentrations of NaCl showed an inverse relationship between the number of days of survival and NaCl concentration in the culture solution.

Similarly, calli that have been cultured in NaCl-enriched medium (15 g NaCl/liter) for 32 mo were placed in different concentrations of NaCl. Calli growth was inversely proportional to the concentration of NaCl in the medium, suggesting that stressed cells have only physiologically adjusted to high NaCl concentrations but are not truly mutants (see table).

Preliminary studies on the chromosome number of the regenerated plants show aneuploidy, a chromosomal abnormality that may have been induced by the prolonged exposure of the calli to the *in vitro* culture conditions.

This is the first report on green plant regeneration from salt-stressed, long-term somatic cell culture. *ST*